

Molecular Diversity Generation through Reactive Lactams^ψ

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Generation of combinatorial libraries has come to occupy a central stage in the search for novel lead structures/pharmacophores needed for new drug discovery research through molecular diversity. In the creation of molecular diversity by synthesis, the synthetic strategies should be short-path, convergent, high yielding and amenable to be carried out under mild conditions. Activated lactams are very suitable for combinatorial synthesis and for creation of molecular diversity. The present review provides an illustrative account of our work on the synthetic utility of activated lactams for creating diverse variety of prototypes by short-path, high yielding synthetic reactions amenable to create a synthetic combinatorial library.

Background

Generation of combinatorial libraries and screening of molecular diversity thus created has come to occupy a central stage in the search for novel lead structures needed for new drug discovery research^{1,2}. Molecular diversity may be derived from chemical laboratory synthesis, from natural products or from biological systems by genetic engineering/manipulation. In the creation of molecular diversity by synthesis, the synthetic strategy and reaction employed therefore are of critical importance. It is useful to have an important pharmacophore, as a central core nucleus, with a polyfunctional reactivity so that diverse types of chemical structures can be built on and around this nucleus. The synthetic reaction used to build the structures on this nucleus should be short-path, convergent, high yielding, and amenable to be carried out under mild conditions, so that a diverse variety of prototype molecules and their analogous and homologous needed can be conveniently prepared. With this objective, pyrrolidine, piperidine and hexahydroazepine were selected as the core structures as these heterocycles are a common pharmacophore of a variety of biodynamic agents. A research programme was therefore initiated to explore the synthetic utility of activated lactams which led to the identification of lactam acetals and thiolactams as reactive species. These possess varied types of chemical reactivity: ability to undergo nucleophilic and electrophilic substitution, cyclocondensation reaction with bifunctional reagents and transacetalization resulting in estrification and alkylation of appropriate substrates³. Lactam acetals can also readily form reactive intermediates, which in turn can react with bifunctional reagents to create another set of heterocyclic and carbocyclic rings, thus adding to the molecular diversity that can be generated. Thus, activated

lactams offer great scope for the creation of molecular diversity. The examples described below are illustrative of the opportunities that activated lactams provide for creating diverse variety of prototypes by short-path, high yielding synthetic operation. This system seems very suitable for creation of synthetic combinatorial libraries, which are under investigation.

Lactam acetals: structure and reactivity

Lactam acetals (1) react with both nucleophiles and electrophiles; with the former at position C-2 and with the latter at C-3³. This phenomenon has been explained assuming the dissociation of acetals into immonium cation 2 and the alkoxide ion. Abstraction of the proton from the cation 2 by the internally generated alkoxide ion very likely leads to formation of the enamine (3). These reactive intermediate species enable the lactam acetals to act both as an electrophile and nucleophile and also form easily alkonium (R₂⁺) species

Scheme 1

^ψDedicated to honour Prof. T. R. Govindachari for his long and outstanding contribution to, and to the cause of, Organic Chemistry and to commemorate his 80th birthday.

by O-R₂ cleavage resulting in C, N, O and S alkylation products **6** (Scheme 1). Lactam acetals, by providing two reactive sites of opposite polarity at C-2 and C-3, condense readily with molecules reactants incorporating suitably disposed nucleophilic and electrophilic centres 2, 3 or 4 atoms apart to form cyclic structures across the C-2 and C-3 sites and are thus of considerable utility for the synthesis of heterocyclic and carbocyclic systems. Chart 1 illustrates the types of condensations studied and different classes of compounds thus synthesized are discussed below.

Chart 1

Pyrrolo[2,3-*e*]indoles :

An elegant and convenient one-pot synthesis of 2,3,7,8-tetrahydropyrrolo[2,3-*e*]indoles (**8**) was achieved by [2+2+2]cyclocondensation of acetophenone or C-acetyl heteroaromatics with excess of pyrrolidinone acetal (**1a**); compounds **8** could also be prepared in a stepwise sequence by reacting equimolar amounts of **1a** and acetophenone to furnish the enaminone (**9**), which on further condensation with **1a** gave rise to **8**. Compounds **8** on dehydrogenation gave pyrrolo[2,3-*e*]indoles in excellent yields⁴.

1,4,7-Trimethyldipyrrolo[2,3-*a* : 2',3'-*c*]carbazole :

Cyclocondensation of lactam acetal **1a** with indole pro-

vides a convenient one-pot synthesis of a novel, hitherto unreported heterocyclic system, 2,3,5,6-tetrahydro-1,4,7-trimethyldipyrrolo[2,3-*a* : 2',3'-*c*]carbazole (**10**), which could also be prepared from 3-(1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinylidene)-3*H*-indole (**11**) obtained by condensation of equimolar amounts of **1a** and indole, followed by reaction of **11** with excess lactam acetal **1a**. Compound **10** on dehydrogenation gave a highly electron-rich heterocyclic system, the dipyrrolo[2,3-*a* : 2',3'-*c*]carbazole (**12**)⁵.

Azacycloalkano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines :

Lactam acetal **1** underwent [2+2+2]cyclocondensation with aryl isocyanates and aryl isothiocyanates to form 3-*N*-arylcabamoyl lactams (**14**) and/or azacycloalkano[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (**13**) depending upon the ring size of the lactam and the reaction conditions used. *N*-Methylpyrrolidinone acetal (**1a**) reacted with both isocyanates and isothiocyanates to form pyrrolo[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (**13**) as the only product. Reaction of 6- and 7-membered acetals (**1b** and **1c**) with aryl isothiocyanates furnished a mixture of 3-*N*-aryltio-carbamoyl lactams (**14**) and pyrido- and azepino[2,3-*d*]pyrimidines (**13**)⁶.

2,4,6-Trisubstituted-1,2-dihydropyrrolo[2,3-*d*]-1,3-dioxanes :

o-Substituted araldehydes on reaction with lactam acetal **1a** first form 2,4,6-trisubstituted-1,2-dihydropyrrolo[2,3-*d*]-1,3-dioxanes (**15**), which undergo facile hydrolysis to the (*R,R*)-benzhydrols **16**; the formation of **15** is particularly favoured with electron-withdrawing substituents. In the reaction of *o*-aminobenzaldehyde, however, the product formed

is tetrahydropyrrolo[2,3-*b*]quinolinol (20). Araldehydes without any *o*-substituent formed *E*-benzylidenepyrrolidinones (17) as the major product along with (*R,S*)-benzhydropyrrolidinones (18) as the minor product^{7,8}.

N,N-Disubstituted-1-alkyl-6-amino-4-aryl-2,3-dihydroindoles :

The cyclocondensation of lactam acetals 1a with 4-atoms unit 1-aryl-3-aminobuten-1-ones (21) led to a new, convenient and general synthesis of *N,N*-disubstituted-1-alkyl-6-amino-4-aryl-2,3-dihydroindoles (22) in one step⁹.

Benz[f]indoles :

Cyclocondensation reaction between pyrrolidinone acetal (1a) and dimethyl homophthalate (23) led to a convenient synthesis of benz[*f*]indoles (24)¹⁰.

*4-Substituted-1-alkyl-6-methyl-2,2-dihydropyrrolo[2,3-*b*]pyridines :*

(2+4)Cyclocondensation reaction of 2,2-dimethoxy-1-alkylpyrrolidines (1) with the enaminones (25) resulted a new and convenient synthesis of 4-substituted-1-alkyl-6-methyl-2,3-dihydropyrrolo[2,3-*b*]pyridines (26)¹¹.

Azacycloalkanopyridones :

Building up pyridine ring across C-2 and C-3 of lactam acetals (1a-c) by [2+4]cyclocondensation includes their reaction with β -aminoesters (27) to form azacycloalkanopyridones (28)¹²⁻¹⁶.

*2,3-Dihydropyrrolo[2,3-*b*]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyridin-4-one*

Cyclocondensation reaction with pyrrolidinone acetal (1a) with methyl β -alaninate (29) led to a convenient synthesis of 2,3-dihydropyrrolo[2,3-*b*]-1,2,3,4-tetrahydropyridin-4-one (30)¹⁷.

7-Deazapurines :

A convenient one-pot synthesis of 7-deazapurine (32) was achieved by [2+4]cyclocondensation of pyrrolidinone acetal (1a) with *N*-acetylthiourea (31)¹⁸.

4-Substituted-6,7-dicarbomethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1-methylindoles :

The enaminone (33) reacted readily with dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate to form 4-alkyl/aryl-6,7-dicarbomethoxy-2,3-dihydro-1-methylindole (34). This transformation constitutes a facile synthesis of polysubstituted indoles presumably via intermediates A and B¹⁹.

Pyrrolophenanthrene :

The reaction of the cyclic enaminone (36), prepared by the condensation of pyrrolidinone acetal (1a) with 4-chromanone and thiochroman-4-one, with dimethyl acetylenedicarboxylate led to the formation of pyrrolophenanthrene (37)²⁰.

Pyrazole and isooxazole derivatives :

Bifunctional nucleophiles such as hydrazine hydrate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride reacted with enaminones 33 and 36, obtained from lactam acetals by reaction with active methylene compounds, to give a facile synthesis of 3- ω -alkylaminopyrazole and -isooxazole 38 and 39, through lactam ring fission^{21,22}. The enaminone 33 (R = CO₂Me) were synthesized by reacting 1-benzyl-5-thioxoprolinate with α -bromoacetophenone which on condensation with hydrozine and hydroxylamine gave ω -substituted unnatural α -amino acids (38)²³.

1'-Methyl-3,4,5,6-tetrahydrospiro(naphth-[2,1-c]-1,2-oxathin-4,2'-pyrrolidine)-2,2-dioxide :

Reaction of sulphene with enaminone 36 gave rise to the spiro compound 40 in excellent yield²².

3-Chloro-4-(γ -N-chloroacetyl-N-methylaminopropyl)-5,6-dihydro-2H-naphtho[1,2-b]pyran-2-one :

The reaction of the cyclic enaminone (36) with chloroketene yielded naphtho[1,2-b]pyranone derivative (41) by the cleavage of the pyrrolidine ring and acylation of the resulting amine with chloroketene²².

Thiophene derivative :

The synthesis of substituted thiophene (44) was achieved by the reaction of the adduct 43 obtained by the reaction of β -nitroenamine (42) with benzoyl isothiocyanate, with phenacyl bromide¹⁰.

Thiazole derivatives :

The reaction of phenacyl bromide with mono- and bisamidines 45 and 46, prepared by the reaction of thiourea with the piperidone and pyrrolidinone acetals 1b and 1a respectively, led to the formation of the 2-substituted-thiazoles 47 and 48 respectively¹⁰.

1,4-Diazabicyclo[4.3.0]nonan-3-one :

The nitroamine (49), possessing *N*-ethoxycarbonylmethyl group, underwent ready reduction accompanied with spontaneous cyclization when hydrogenated over Raney-nickel to furnish 1,4-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]nonan-3-one (50)²⁴. The piperazinone (50) had been synthesized earlier in multi-steps by Schmidt reaction on 1-azabicyclo[3.3.0]octan-3-one.

***D*(1-methylazacycloalkeno)[2,3-*b* 2',3'-*d*]pyridines :**

N-Benzoylamidines (51), prepared by the reaction of primary amides with lactam acetals 1a and 1b, reacted with pyrrolidinone acetal 1a to form 2-benzoylimino-1-methyl-3-(1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinylidene)pyrrolidine (52) which furnished tetrahydrodipyrrolo[2,3-*b* : 2',3'-*d*]pyridine (53) on intramolecular cyclization with phosphorus oxychloride which on dehydrogenation provided a facile synthesis of dipyrrolo[2,3-*b* : 2',3'-*d*]pyridines (54). Piperidone acetal (1b) on reacting with *N*-benzoylamidines (51) furnished directly the cyclized products (55)²⁵. The ring system dipyrrolo[2,3-*b* : 2',3'-*d*]pyridine[5,6,5] and pyrrolo[3,2-*c*]-1,8-naphthyridine[5,6,6] are hitherto not known in literature while the formation of the parent pyrido[2,3-*h*]-1,6-naphthyridine[6,6,6] was reported only as byproduct in the Hofmann reaction of 2,3'-bipyridine-2',3-dicarboxamide.

***Pyrrolo- and pyrido*[2,3-*b*]quinolines :**

The reaction of pyrrolidinone acetal (1a) and piperidone acetal (1b) with *N*-acetylisatin and 5-chloro-*N*-acetylisatin (56) led to novel pyrrolo- and pyrido[2,3-*b*]quinolines (58) along with the hydroxy intermediate (57)²⁶.

(+)-(1*S*, 5*R*)- and (-)-(1*R*, 5*S*)-3,8-Diazabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-2-ones :

Making use of amide activation chiral synthesis of (+)-(1*S*, 5*R*)- and (-)-(1*R*, 5*S*)-3,8-diazabicyclo[3.2.1]octan-2-ones 59, 60 has been achieved from L- and D-pyrroglutamates. The key step of the synthesis involves a stereoselective catalytic hydrogenation, accompanied with spontaneous cyclization of the nitroamines 61, 62²⁷. This ring system had been synthesized earlier but without any consideration to chirality.

(-)-(2*R*, 6*S*)-, (-)-(2*S*, 6*S*)-, (+)-(2*S*, 6*R*)-, (+)-(2*R*, 6*R*)-2-Methyl-1,4-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]nonan-5-ones :

Making use of amide activation chiral synthesis of (-)-(2*R*, 6*S*)-, (-)-(2*S*, 6*S*)-, (+)-(2*S*, 6*R*)-, (+)-(2*R*, 6*R*)-2-methyl-1,4-diazabicyclo[4.3.0]nonan-5-ones 63, 64, 65 and 66 has

been achieved from L- and D-proline methyl esters respectively, via stereoselective catalytic hydrogenation of the nitroenamines **67**, **68** accompanied with spontaneous cyclization. Both 2*R* and 2*S* diastereoisomers were obtained with 40% d.e. of the diastereomer with 2-CH₃ oriented *cis* to the 6-H²⁷.

4-β-(2-Heterocycloalkyl)quinoline-4-ethanols :

A convenient synthetic strategy to 4-β-(2-heterocycloalkyl)quinoline-4-ethanols (**72**) has been developed which involves condensation of quinoline-4-acetic acid methyl ester (**69**) with lactam acetals (**1a** and **1b**) and lactim ether (**70**) followed by hydride reduction of the condensation products **71**²⁸.

4-[2-(1-Azacycloalkyl)methyl]quinolinones :

Reaction of 4-bromomethyl-1,2-dihydroquinolin-2-one (**73**) with lactam acetals (**1a** and **1b**) in presence of zinc (Reformatsky condition) yielded *N*-alkyl-2-[4-(2-oxoquinolyl)methylene]-1-azacycloalkanes (**74**), the key intermediates for the synthesis of antimalarial quinoline-4-methanols (**75**)²⁹.

Perspective

Azacycloalkane ($N<$) is a common structural unit/synthon present in a variety of natural products. Azacycloalkanes are also an important pharmacophore of a variety of biodynamic agents. Ability to functionalize/substitute azacycloalkanes at different positions specially pyrrolidines and piperidines, and to build hetero and aromatic ring on them, or through them, is of great synthetic importance both to synthesize natural products and also to get ready entry to different types of heterocyclic systems needed in search of biologically active compounds.

The reactions described in the report indicate the scope and versatility that lactams and their activated forms offer for nucleophilic, electrophilic and cyclo-addition reactions, and for building different reactive structural units on them to construct carbocyclic and heterocyclic systems. The more important synthetic aspects which emerge from these studies are as follows. (i) It is possible to functionalize and

introduce substituents in lactam directly or through their activated forms at positions 2 and 5 with nucleophiles, and at positions 1 and 3 with electrophiles. This offers the possibility of synthesizing substituted azacycloalkanes and also to build rings on them by condensing with bifunctional reagents.

(ii) It has also been shown that enaminones ($X = CH$), and their aza analogs ($X = N$), both obtained readily and in good yields from lactam acetals, are versatile intermediates for : (a) building aromatic carbocyclic and heterocyclic rings on the azacycloalkane platform (path A), and (b) ready entry to side-chain ω -functionalized alkylheterocycles by ring transformation reaction (path B),

References

- 1 M R PAVIA, T K SAWYER, and W H MOODS, *Bioorg Med Chem Lett*, 1993, 3, 381
- 2 (a) P J HYLANDS and L J NISBET, *Annu Rep Med Chem*, 1991, 26, 259, (b) W H MOOS, G D GREEN, and M R PAVIA, *Annu Rep Med Chem*, 1993, 28, 315
- 3 N ANAND and J SINGH, *Tetrahedron*, 1988, 44, 5975
- 4 P AHUJA, J SINGH, and N ANAND, Unpublished result
- 5 P AHUJA, J SINGH, and N ANAND, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1983, 22, 723
- 6 J SINGH, V VIRMANI, P C JAIN, and N ANAND, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1980, 19, 195
- 7 V VIRMANI, J SINGH, P C JAIN, and N ANAND, *J Chem, Soc Pak*, 1979, 1, 109
- 8 J SINGH, V SARDANA, and N ANAND, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1983, 22, 1079
- 9 P AHUJA, J SINGH, and N ANAND, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1983, 22, 1142
- 10 M B NIGAM, Ph D Thesis, Lucknow University, 1980
- 11 P AHUJA, J SINGH, and N ANAND, *Indian J Chem, Sect B*, 1988, 27, 166

12. V. VIRMANI, Ph.D. Thesis, Lucknow University, 1977.
13. V. G. GRANIK, A. M. ZHIDKOVA, S. S. KISLEV, R. G. GLUSHKOV, A. I. POLEZHAeva, and A. I. MASHKOVSKII, *Khim. Farm. Zh.*, 1978, 12, 66.
14. A. M. ZHIDKOVA, V. G. GRANIK, R. G. GLUSHKOV, T. F. VALSOVA, O. S. ANISIMOVA, T. A. GUS'KOVA, and G. N. PERSIN, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin.*, 1974, 670.
15. V. G. GRANIK, N. B. MARCHENKO, and R. G. GLUSHKOV, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin.*, 1978, 1549.
16. E. O. SOCHNEVA, N. P. SOLOV'EVA, and V. G. GRANIK, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin.*, 1978, 1671.
17. P. AHUJA, J. SINGH, M. B. ASTHANA, V. SARDANA, and N. ANAND, Unpublished result.
18. J. SINGH and N. ANAND, Unpublished result.
19. P. AHUJA, J. SINGH, and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1982, 21, 142.
20. P. AHUJA, Ph.D. Thesis, Lucknow University, 1983.
21. V. VIRMANI, M. B. NIGAM, P. C. JAIN and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 17, 472.
22. J. SINGH, V. SARDANA, P. C. JAIN, and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 1083.
23. S. JAIN and N. ANAND, Unpublished results.
24. J. SINGH, Ph.D. Thesis, Banaras University, 1982.
25. S. JAIN, R. JAIN, J. SINGH, and N. ANAND, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, 31, 131.
26. J. SINGH, V. SARDANA, and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, 28, 1031.
27. S. JAIN, K. SUJATHA, K. V. RAMA KRISHNA, R. ROY, J. SINGH, and N. ANAND, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, 48, 4985.
28. R. JAIN, S. JAIN, J. SINGH, and N. ANAND, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1994, 33, 747.
29. S. JAIN, R. JAIN, J. SINGH, and N. ANAND, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, 35, 2951.